

Table 3 continued

Characters	Cross	Direct effect		Indirect effect				Phenotypic correlation value with single-plant yield	
		F ₂	F ₃	Harvest index		Dry matter production		F ₂	F ₃
				F ₂	F ₃	F ₂	F ₃		
Grain no./panicle	ASD1/Co 33	-0.07	-0.01	0.04	0.01	0.28	0.32	0.29	0.32
	ASD1/ADT36	0.06	0.01	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.17	0.15
	ASD1/IR50	-0.06	0.01	0.08	0.09	0.30	0.13	0.40**	0.21
100-grain weight	ASD1/Co 33	0.08	-0.01	0.02	-0.08	0.11	0.06	0.20	-0.03
	ASD1/ADT36	-0.03	0.03	0.03	0.20	0.06	0.04	0.07	0.27
	ASD1/IR50	-0.01	0.01	0.03	-0.02	-0.02	0.01	0.01	-0.03
	Residual effect								
		F ₂	F ₃						
	ASD1/Co 33	0.16	0.06						
	ASD1/ADT36	0.12	0.09						
	ASD1/IR50	0.17	0.07						

**Significant at the 1% level. *Significant at 5% level.

Near-isogenic pairs of indica rices with blast (BI) resistance genes

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Rice BI-resistant near-isogenic pairs involving resistant lines with different genes and corresponding susceptible lines facilitate systematic genetic analysis and molecular study of BI re-

sistance. Each pair has a highly uniform genetic background; they presumably differ only in the resistance genes.

We crossed resistant cultivars Ai-jiao-bai-mi-zi, Tetep, and IR58 with the susceptible recurrent parent Zhen-shan 97. Plants segregating for resistance to Chinese BI races ZB15 and ZC15 were selected for successive selfing generations to produce resistant and susceptible lines (see figure). Reactions to Chinese BI races ZB15,

Reaction of near-isogenic pairs to 3 Chinese rice BI fungus races. Hangzhou, China.

Isogenic pairs	Resistance donor	Reaction ^a		
		ZB15	ZC15	ZF1
H1 R and H5 R	Ai-jiao-bai-mi-zi	R	R	S
H1 S and H5 S		S	S	S
H2 R and H3 R		R	R	R
H2 S and H3 S		S	S	S
H4 R and H6 R		R	R	R
H4 S and H6 S		S	S	R
H7 R	Tetep	R	R	R
H7 S		S	S	S
H8 R	IR58	R	R	R
H8 S		S	S	R
H9 R		R	R	S
H9 S		S	S	R
H10 R		S	R	R
H10 S		S	S	S

^a R = resistant, S = susceptible.

ZC15, and ZF1 of 10 near-isogenic pairs differed (see table).

Studies on the molecular biology of rice BI resistance are under way using the pairs. □

Procedure for selecting near-isogenic pair H1 R and H1 S. Lines were backcrossed three times then BC₃ plants were selfed 9 times to produce BC₃F₁₀R and S lines. Selection of other pairs was similar. R = resistant, S = susceptible.

Breeding methods

Anther culturability of rice lines bearing cytoplasmic male sterility

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An increase of anther culturability in cytoplasmic male sterile lines relative to male fertile varieties has been reported in wheat and tobacco. We did a similar study in rice.

The wild abortive cytoplasm (WA), which usually promotes microspore abortion at the uninucleate stage, and the Chinsurah Boro II cytoplasm (BT), which usually triggers a late degeneration of the pollen grains between the binucleated and trinucleated stage, were introduced by successive backcrosses into upland rice varieties IRAT313, IRAT103, and IRAT177.

Cytological observations showed apparently identical aspects of the

microspores excised from male sterile and male fertile panicles at the anther plating stage (i.e., the mid-uninucleate stage).

The callus-forming ability of the anthers of the male sterile lines appears to be related to the stage of pollen abortion (see table). When late abortion occurs (BT cytoplasm), the anther culturability of the male sterile lines is either slightly decreased or not significantly different from control. When male sterility is due to early microspore degeneration (WA cytoplasm), a dramatic decrease in callus production occurs, because the microspore population that undergoes the androgenesis pathway is consistently reduced.

Induction ability of male sterile rice lines and their male fertile homologue lines. Goias, Brazil.

Genotype	Cytoplasm	Callus-forming	Pollen sterility	Spikelet
		anthers/anther inoculated ^a	just before anthesis ^b	sterility ^c
		(%)	(%I)	(%)
IRAT313	Normal	5 a	7	21
CNA-IRAT1A	WA	0 b	98	100
IRAT103	Normal	25 a	3	12
CNA-IRAT6A	WA	8b	37	100
CNA-IRAT4A	BT	22 a	5	99
IRAT177	Normal	29 a	3	17
CNA-IRAT12A	BT	15 b	3	100

^a Mean percentages of 2 replications of 600 anthers each. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b Mean percentages of 3 observations of 100 pollen grains each. ^c Mean percentages of 3 bagged panicles.

This decrease in anther culturability of lines bearing the male sterile cytoplasm is the reverse of reports of

anther culturability in wheat and tobacco. □

Hybrid sterility in interracial and interspecific rice crosses

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Hybrid sterility in early generations of interracial and interspecific rice crosses is due to genic and cryptic structural hybridity. We examined the F₁s from eight japonica/indica, six japonica/japonica-indica, and two interspecific crosses during Jun-Sep 1988.

Spikelet sterility at harvest was 37.5-91.6%. Grain fertility was 8.4-62.5% (see table). Grain fertility of the

parents was 85.9-95.5%. In crosses involving the same parent as male or female, grain fertility differed greatly because of gene interaction.

Derivatives of japonica/indica crosses crossed with japonicas behaved like indicas and did not improve grain fertility, except in Nakate Shinsenbon/Ponni (fertility = 62.5%).

Hybrid sterility in the F₁ makes it difficult to generate large numbers of F₂ plants with desirable characters. Anther culture of F₁ hybrids to capture difficult-to-recover plant characters and to gain quick homozygosity is being attempted using F₁ stubbles of these interracial and interspecific crosses. □

Fertility in the F₁ of interracial, interspecific rice crosses. Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

Cross	F ₁ grain fertility (%)
<i>Japonica/indica</i>	
Norin 8/TKM6-35 kr.	42.1
Norin 8/IR50	21.0
Zuhio/ASD16	8.4
Zuhio/CO 37	11.1
Zuhio/IR50	12.1
Oozora/CO 37	47.6
Oozora/IR50	11.3
Nakate Shinsenbon/IR50	26.2
<i>Japonica/japonica-indica</i>	
Norin 6/Ponni	10.7
Norin 6/Ponni dwarf	14.8
Norin 8/White Ponni	39.8
Norin 8/Ponni dwarf	13.4
Oozora/Ponni	19.1
Nakate Shinsenbo/Ponni	62.5
<i>Interspecific</i>	
<i>O. sativa f. spontanea</i> /ADT 37	11.7
<i>O. sativa f. spontanea</i> /Ponni dwarf	14.1

Using metroglyph analysis to study variability in early generations of rainfed lowland rice

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We studied the morphological variations in 12 F₂ families obtained from 9 parents under semidry conditions in 1988. Panicle length, tillers per plant, plant height, and single plant yield were recorded from 50 single plants per family selected for extreme differences (see table).

Variability in the F₂ populations was expressed in metroglyph analysis using score indices. A scatter diagram was

plotted using plant height as the ordinate and single plant yield as the abscissa. Variation in other characters was represented by range and direction (see figure).

Index values for the range of variability were partitioned into four groups using class intervals. The range of variation was wider in Norungan/IR50 (index value 15) and IR29/IR50 (index value 13).